

**INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF NEW CAPACITIES
ESTABLISHED BY SMALL BUSINESSES AND ENTREPRENEURIAL
ENTITIES WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF INVESTMENT PROGRAMS
IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY**

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Abstract: The purpose of this study is to analyze the implementation of the system of comprehensive assistance to small businesses and entrepreneurial entities to organize the effective use of capacities established within the framework of investment programs. In this, it was highlighted that the support of business entities is important for the further development of the economy of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: small business and entrepreneurial entities, post-investment monitoring system, national economy, production capacity, export potential.

The development of the country's economy based on different forms of property, based on the requirements of the market economy, is considered one of the most urgent tasks of the current period. The role of small business and private entrepreneurship is increasing, based on competition, in the development of the national economy.

In recent years, Uzbekistan, reformed the national economy, liberalized foreign trade, tax, and financial policy, supported entrepreneurship and guaranteed the integrity of private property, organized deep processing of agricultural products, and ensured the rapid development of regions, legislative reforms are being carried out and through this, attention is paid to the production of competitive, exportable and high-margin products in the world market.

In particular, during 2017-2023, he made revolutionary decisions to support private business, which is the driver of the modern economy. More than two hundred licenses and permits were cancelled in this field. The total number of taxes was reduced

from 13 to 9, some tax rates were reduced by 2 times. From 2023, the value added tax rate has been reduced from 15% to 12%.

Due to these created opportunities, due to the direction of investments by small businesses and private business entities in the further development of industrial sectors, the volume of production of industrial products in the regions is increasing year by year. In particular, by the end of 2022, small businesses and private enterprises will produce 143.9 trillion soums worth of industrial products, which has increased by 2.3 times compared to 2017.

Also, in 2022, compared to 2017, the volume of services increased by 2.6 times, the volume of trade by 2.5 times, the volume of agricultural products by 2.3 times, and the volume of export products by 2.1 times.

To achieve these target indicators, within the framework of investment programs adopted in 2017-2022, business entities have invested nearly 62.1 billion dollars, and 60.8 thousand projects have been implemented. Due to these projects, 342.5 trillion soums of production (services) capacities and 1.1 mln. creation of new jobs has been achieved. The created jobs accounted for 8% of the employed population of our republic.

In addition, 20,900 industrial projects with a total value of 39.4 billion dollars have been launched by entrepreneurs of our republic involving foreign partners during 2017-2022. Due to these, production capacities worth 321.8 trillion soums per year were created and more than 533 thousand jobs were created.

Due to the creation of new industrial enterprises, modernization, and expansion of existing ones within the framework of investment programs, industrial products worth 1.8 billion dollars were exported in 2017 alone, and by the end of 2022, industrial products worth 4.5 billion dollars will be exported, or 2.5 billion compared to 2017. double growth has been achieved.

Also, due to the newly created capacities, the production of industrial products in the regions increased by 3.7 times in 2022 compared to 2017. Especially Navoi (6.5

times), Jizzakh (4.5 m.), Khorezm (4.5 m.), Tashkent (4.3 m.), Jizzakh (4.2 m.), and Andijan (4. 1 m.) the volume of production of industrial products increased sharply in the regions.

By the end of 2022, the share of small business and entrepreneurship in the gross domestic product was 51.8 percent, in industry 26 percent, in construction 71.5 percent, in employment 73.9 percent, and in exports 29.6 percent.

Acceleration of investment processes is of great and decisive importance for the improvement of the country's economy, and the construction and reconstruction of new enterprises equipped with modern equipment and technologies. Foremost, it provides an opportunity to solve the most important social problems, such as increasing the employment of the population, wages, and income. That is why it is one of the most important issues to make full use of the capacities created at the expense of investments in our country and to provide economic stimulation and necessary conditions for enterprises that achieve this.

Uzbekistan of the President of the Republic of December 28, 2020

With the decision of PQ-4937, the Department of Post-Investment Monitoring was established in the Ministry of Investments, Industry, and Trade, and its main task is to analyze the level of utilization of production facilities and facilities created within the framework of investment programs, technical and economic analysis of investment projects. The project initiators were assigned the task of helping to achieve the indicators.

For 3 years, the established department has been coordinating the post-investment monitoring of relevant state administration bodies, organizations, economic associations, the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions, and Tashkent city administrations in projects launched within the framework of investment programs.

In particular, state administration bodies, organizations, economic associations, the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and regional and Tashkent

city administrations go to places and study the level of utilization of production capacities in enterprises every month. In particular, the implementation of the production (services) plans on the technical economical basis and business plans of the projects are studied. Proportion is determined by comparing the actual production volumes with the established plans for production (services) capacities in enterprises.

Determining the reasons for the decrease in production volume, proposals for their elimination will be developed and submitted to the Investment Projects Post Monitoring Department of the Ministry of Investments, Industry and Trade.

The department of post-monitoring of investment projects has compiled the received proposals, in agreement with the relevant ministries and agencies, developed a plan of measures aimed at solving the existing systemic and individual problems of bringing production to full capacity in enterprises operating at low capacity, and the Republic of Uzbekistan It will be submitted for approval to the Government Commission on Foreign Trade, Investments, Development of Local Industry and Technical Regulation.

Relevant state administration bodies, organizations, economic associations, and the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions, and Tashkent city administrations will be monitored for the implementation of the approved measures, and information will be submitted to the Government Commission.

Based on this system, to organize the effective use of the capacities created by business entities in the fields of industry, service, and agriculture, post-monitoring works are carried out every month, and measures are being implemented to solve the identified problematic issues.

During the year 2023, the problematic issues that harm the production process of the enterprises that were launched as part of the investment programs in 2017-2022, but are working at low capacity, are identified and focused on implementation.

In particular, 878 different problematic issues affecting the production process of 731 enterprises were positively resolved by relevant ministries and agencies. As a

result, the existing production capacities of 24.5 trillion soums, export opportunities of 149.6 million dollars, and more than 25.9 thousand jobs were restored in these enterprises.

Extensive work will be continued to improve the business environment by radically increasing the role and role of private property in the economy, creating the necessary conditions and opportunities for the rapid development of private property and private entrepreneurship, and expanding their use of material and credit resources.

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